

Negative news can discourage future teachers

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Summary

1. Negative media coverage about education can reduce young people's intention to become teachers.
2. Students strongly underestimate teachers' job satisfaction, suggesting unnecessary pessimism about the teaching profession.
3. About 40% of students report that negative news about education quality has lowered their interest in becoming a teacher.
4. Short, factual and positive information about trust in teachers and their social contribution increases teaching intentions among students in teacher education.
5. Policy should promote accurate, nuanced and credible communication about the teaching profession.

1. Introduction

Teacher shortages are one of the major challenges facing education systems. At the same time, public debate about education is often dominated by negative news. Headlines about declining learning outcomes, schools facing severe teacher shortages and problematic student behaviour are hard to ignore. These issues are real and deserve serious attention. Yet the way they are communicated may also have unintended consequences.

This policy brief discusses evidence on how negative news and positive information affect young people's intention to become teachers.

The central question is straightforward: does a crisis narrative about education discourage students from entering the teaching profession? And can accurate positive information correct overly negative perceptions?

The study shows that young people are often unnecessarily pessimistic about teaching. They strongly underestimate teachers' job satisfaction. While international evidence shows that a very large share of teachers are satisfied with their job, students believe this share is much lower. This points to a gap between perception and reality.

This matters for policy. Study choices and career decisions are not only based on facts. They are also shaped by images, expectations

and public narratives. If the public debate focuses mainly on shortages, declining performance and crisis, it may reduce the attractiveness of teaching. In this way, negative news can, over time, contribute to the very problem it reports on.

The findings do not imply that problems in education should be hidden or downplayed. On the contrary, policymakers, media and education stakeholders should continue to discuss education quality and teacher shortages openly. However, this debate should be accurate, nuanced and placed in context. This is essential to address real problems while keeping teaching attractive for future generations.

2. Data and Methodology

The research is based on two experiments in Flanders. The first experiment examined whether negative news about education quality reduces the intention to become a teacher. The study included 1,071 young people: 375 students in upper secondary education and 696 students in the final years of a professional or academic bachelor's programme.

Participants were randomly assigned to two groups. One group saw real newspaper headlines and short text fragments about declining education quality, based on international studies such as PISA and PIRLS. The control group saw neutral news items about unrelated topics. Participants were then asked how likely they were to choose the teaching profession.

The second experiment focused on 589 students enrolled in teacher education. They received factual positive information about public trust in teachers and the value of

teachers' contribution to society. The study then measured whether this information increased their intention to apply for a teaching job after graduation.

This design makes it possible to move beyond simple correlations and test whether information itself affects career intentions. The brief also follows guidance on writing policy briefs by focusing on clear messages, actionable recommendations and evidence-based conclusions.

3. Results

The first experiment shows that negative news lowers the intention to become a teacher. Students exposed to negative news about education quality reported an intention to become a teacher that was almost 2 percentage points lower. This corresponds to a decline of around 6%.

At first sight, this effect may seem small. However, it can be meaningful over time. If small effects are repeated across several cohorts of students, they can cumulatively contribute to teacher shortages. Even if only part of the short-term effect on intentions translates into actual career choices, the societal impact may still be relevant.

The survey evidence points in the same direction. Around 40% of students said that negative news about education quality had reduced their interest in the teaching profession. Most described the effect as limited, but the finding confirms that the public image of education plays a role in career choices.

A striking result is that students strongly underestimate teacher job satisfaction. Evidence shows that 93% of teachers are satisfied with their job, but young people

estimate this figure at only around 55% to 60%. Almost no student estimated the figure correctly. This suggests that the teaching profession faces not only objective challenges, but also an information problem.

The second experiment shows that positive, factual information can help. Teacher education students who received information about public trust in teachers and their social contribution reported a 5 percentage point higher intention to teach after graduation. This is a clear effect, especially given that the intervention was short and simple.

Together, the results show that communication matters. Negative news can discourage potential teachers, while accurate positive information can reduce doubts and strengthen teaching intentions.

4. Policy Recommendations

1. Put education challenges in context. Policymakers and education stakeholders should continue to communicate clearly about declining learning outcomes and teacher shortages. However, these figures should be presented alongside broader information on working conditions, job satisfaction, autonomy, social value and career opportunities. A one-sided crisis narrative may discourage young people from entering teaching.

2. Actively correct misperceptions. Students strongly underestimate teachers' job satisfaction. Accurate information about the profession should therefore become part of study guidance, teacher education and public communication. This is not about advertising, but about ensuring that young people can make career choices based on facts rather than distorted perceptions.

3. Develop credible communication campaigns. Campaigns should focus on intrinsic motivation, social impact and the real trust teachers enjoy. The message must remain factual and honest. Purely promotional slogans that do not reflect reality risk missing their target or even becoming counterproductive.

4. Work with teacher education institutions and schools. Students in teacher education are a key target group, because not all graduates enter the profession. Short information interventions about social appreciation and public trust may help convince students who are uncertain about becoming teachers.

5. Monitor the public image of teaching. Teacher shortages are influenced not only by pay, workload and working conditions, but also by expectations and public narratives. Policymakers should regularly assess how young people perceive teaching and where misperceptions arise.

What is EFFeCt ?

EFFeCt is an impact-driven research project aiming to enhance the quality of education in the EU by providing evidence-based policy recommendations and conducting rigorous research on the education policies of individual EU member states.

Further Information:

Based on De Cort, W. & De Witte, K. (2026). Media coverage, social status and students' teaching aspirations: evidence from two RCTs. Working paper published as De Cort, W. (2026). The Right to Learn at Risk? On the Causes and Solutions to Teacher Shortages and Tutoring markets. Doctoral dissertation, KU Leuven.

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